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SOCIAL COMPETENCE OF SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN RELATION TO SELF-CONFIDENCE

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Abstract

The main objective of present study was to find out the relationship between Social Competence and Self Confidence of Government senior secondary school students. To achieve this objective, social competence scale (SCS) by V.P. Sharma, Prabha Shukla and Kiran Shukla (1992) and Self-confidence inventory by Dr. M. Baswana (1971) were used. The sample consists of 200 students of various government senior secondary school selected randomly from Ludhiana District of Punjab, India. The sample was equally categorized between Boys – Girls and Arts – Science Students. The results revealed that there exists a significant relationship between self confidence and social competence of Government Senior Secondary School Students. It means that self confidence affects the social competence of Government Senior Secondary School Students.

Key Words:

Social Competence, Self Confidence, Government Senior Secondary School Students.

INTRODUCTION

Self-Confidence is characterized by: assertiveness, optimism, eagerness, affection, pride, independence, trust, the ability to handle criticism, emotional maturity and the ability to accurately assess our capabilities whereas social competence refers to the social, emotional and

cognitive skills. The strength of belief is one's key to self-confidence. Self-confidence plays a vital role in the social competence of Government Senior Secondary School Students.. Children who have a wide repertoire of social skills and who are socially aware perceptive are likely to be socially competent. Social competence is the broader term used to describe a child's social effectiveness.

SELF CONFIDENCE

The faith or belief in one's own strength and ability is Self-Confidence; one of the traits of good personality is Self-Confidence. It leads to self-Integrity and Self fulfillment. Self-Confidence is a faith in one's ability. Self-Integrity refers to harmony between the actual self (what you are) and desired self (What you want to become) where as Self-fulfillment refers to saying all the needs of the individual (C.V Good).

Self-Confidence is a positive attitude of oneself—one's self concept. Self-Confidence refers to a person's perceived ability to tackle situations successfully without learning on others and to have a positive self-evaluation. Baswana (1975) defines "Self-Confidence refers to an individual's perceived ability to act efficiently in a situation to overcome obstacles and to get things go all right." Self-Confidence has so shaped man's personality that he is well prepared to play his roles and his basic needs are met by playing such roles.

SOCIAL COMPETENCE

Social competence refers to the social, emotional & cognitive skills and behaviors that children need for successful social adaptation. Despite this simple definition, social competence is an elusive concept skills and behaviors required for healthy social development vary with the age of the child and with the demands of particular situations. A socially competent preschool child behaves in a much different manner than a socially competent adolescent; conversely the same behaviors (e.g. aggression, shyness) have different implications for social adaptation depending upon the age of the child.

A child's social competence depends upon a number of factors including the child's social skills, social awareness and self-confidence. During adolescence, peer relations become particularly important for children. A key developmental task of adolescence is the formation of an identity—a sense of the kind of person you are and the kind of person you want to be. Adolescents "try on" different social roles as they interact with peers and peers serve as a social

"stepping stone" as Adolescents move away from their emotional dependence upon their parents and toward autonomous functioning as an adult. In many ways, then, childhood peer relations serve as "training grounds" for future interpersonal relations, providing children with opportunities to learn about reciprocity and intimacy. These skills are associated with effective interpersonal relations in adult life, including relations with co-workers and with romantic partners.

Review of Literature

The author has reviewed the literature so as to get better insight of the research problem and elucidated following research works viz. In a study [3] the authors examined that Social competence includes not only behaviors but also cognitive skills which directs and facilitate children's social behaviors.

In study [4] "role taking and social competence in autism and mental retardation" suggested that individual with autism show deficits in social cognitive abilities when compared with non autistic persons matched for mental age. These defects have been proposed as a basic for social interaction difficulties seen in autistic persons. In the present study, autistic youth were compared with a matched group of non autistic mentally retarded youth on three role-taking tasks and three measures of social competence. Results indicated that the autistic group was relatively deficient on each of the social competence measures and on one of the role taking measures. The role taking measure on which the groups differed also correlated significantly with each of the social competence measures. Results were discussed in terms of the interplay between social cognitive abilities and social interaction.

In study [8] "social competence among children with central nervous system-related chronic health conditions" reviewed empirical studies of social competence among children with central nervous system (CNS) related chronic health conditions published since 1975. The overwhelming majority of studies evaluated social competence at the level of social adjustment; the domains of children's social performance and social skills were relatively neglected (cavell,1990). Findings are critiqued with respect to conceptualization of social competence among children with CNS conditions and methodological considerations. Directions for future research include expanding the conceptualization of social competence in this population to

include social demands and competencies specific to children with CNS conditions and utilizing explicit theoretical frameworks that allow for competing hypotheses to be tested.

In study [10] author conducted a study on “self confidence in relation to emotional maturity” and found that there exists significant relationship between self confidence and emotional maturity among the senior secondary school students.

In study [13] the author concluded that parental attitude played a significant role in developing self-confidence ratings among children.

Objectives

The study was carried out with the following objectives:

1. To study the Social Competence of Government Senior Secondary School Students.
2. To study the Social Competence of Government Senior Secondary School Students with respect to gender.
3. To study the Social Competence of Government Senior Secondary School Students with respect to streams.
4. To study the Self-Confidence of Government Senior Secondary School Students.
5. To study the Self-Confidence of Government Senior Secondary School Students with respect to gender.
6. To study the Self-Confidence of Government Senior Secondary School Students with respect to streams.
7. To study the relationship between Social Competence and Self-Confidence of Government Senior Secondary School Students.

Hypotheses

In order to achieve the above said objectives of the study following Hypothesis were formulated:

1. There will be significant difference in the mean scores of social competence of Government Senior Secondary School Students with respect to gender.
2. There will be significant difference in the mean scores of social competence of Government Senior Secondary School Students of Science and Arts streams.

3. There will be significant difference in the mean scores of self-confidence of Government Senior Secondary School Students with respect to gender.
4. There will be significant difference in the mean scores of self-confidence of Government Senior Secondary School Students of Science and Arts streams.
5. There will be significant relationship between social competence and self-confidence of Government Senior Secondary School Students.

Delimitations of the study

The study was carried out with the following Delimitations:

1. The study was delimited to Ludhiana District of Punjab, India only.
2. The study was delimited to Government Senior Secondary School Students.
3. The study was delimited to 200 Government Senior Secondary School Students only.
4. The study was delimited to 100 Male and 100 Female Government Senior Secondary School Students only.
5. The Study was delimited to 100 Science and 100 Arts stream Government Senior Secondary School Students only.

Method

Keeping in view the nature of the study, Descriptive research method was used in the present study.

Sample

The present study was conducted on 200 Government Senior Secondary School Students of Ludhiana district of Punjab, India. The sample was selected by simple random method of probability sampling. The sample was equally categorized between Boys – Girls and Arts – Science.

Tools used

The selection of suitable tool and their application is an important step in the collection of data after the research problem has been selected, defined and delimited. The collected data should be sufficient, reliable and valid. For the reliability and validity of data, following tools was used in the present study:

- Social Competence scale by V.P. Sharma, Prabha Shukla and Kiran Shukla (1992).

- Self-confidence inventory by Dr. M. Baswana (1971).

Statistical techniques used

Statistical techniques viz. Mean, Standard Deviation (S.D), Critical ratio (t-test) and Co-efficient of correlation (r) were used to analyse and interpret the collected data.

Analysis and Interpretation

The results of the present study are elucidated as below:

Table I

showing the Mean, Standard Deviation (S.D.), Standard Error of Difference (S.E_D) and t-ratio of Social Competence of 100 Males and 100 Females Government Senior Secondary School Students.

Group	N	Mean	S.D.	SE _D	t-Ratio	Level of Significance
Male	100	168.11	23.96	1.210	2.75**	Significant at 0.05 and 0.01 levels of significant
Female	100	170.86	20.68			

From table-I it is found that ‘t’-value of social competence of 100 males and 100 females Government Senior Secondary School Students is 0.275 which is significant at 0.05 and 0.01 level of significance. Hence, there is significant difference in the social competence of males and females Government Senior Secondary School Students. Hence the **Hypothesis-I** “There will be significant difference in the mean scores of social competence of Government Senior Secondary School Students with respect to gender” is accepted.

Table II

Showing the Mean, Standard Deviation (S.D.), Standard Error of Difference (S.E_D) and t-ratio of Social Competence of 100 Science and 100 Arts Government Senior Secondary School Students.

Variable	N	Mean	S.D.	S.E _D	t-ratio	Level of significance
Science Students	100	64.16	13.55	0.484	2.67**	Significant at 0.05 and 0.01 level of significance
Arts Students	100	62.87	12.66			

From table-II it is found that ‘t-value’ of social competence of 100 Science and 100 Arts Government Senior Secondary School Students is 2.67 which is significant at 0.05 and 0.01 level of significance. Hence, there is significant difference in the social competence of Science and Arts Government Senior Secondary School Students. Hence the Hypothesis-II “There will be significant difference in the mean scores of social competence of Government Senior Secondary School Students of Science and Arts streams” is accepted.

Table III

Mean, Standard Deviation (S.D.), Standard Error of Difference (S.E_D) and t-ratio of Self Confidence of 100 Males and 100 Females Government Senior Secondary School Students.

Group	N	M	S.D.	SE _D	t- Ratio	Level of Significance
Female	100	64.04	12.66	0.410	4.32**	Significant at 0.05 and 0.01 level of significant.
Male	100	62.27	11.98			

From table-III it is found that ‘t’-value of self confidence of 100 males and 100 females Government Senior Secondary School Students is 4.32 which is significant at 0.05 and 0.01 level of significance. Hence, there is significant difference in the social competence of males and females Government Senior Secondary School Students. Hence the Hypothesis-III “There will be significant difference in the mean scores of self-confidence of Government Senior Secondary School Students with respect to gender” is accepted.

Table IV

Mean, Standard Deviation (S.D.), Standard Error of Difference (S.E_D) and t-ratio of Self Confidence of 100 Science and 100 Arts Government Senior Secondary School Students.

Group	N	M	SD	S.E.D.	t-ratio	Level of Significant
Science Students	100	173.5	23.72	0.789	6.62**	Significant at 0.05 and
Arts Students	100	168.28	21.89			0.01 level of significant.

From table-IV it is found that ‘t-value’ of self confidence of 100 Science and 100 Arts Government Senior Secondary School Students is 6.62 which is significant at 0.05 and 0.01 level of significance. Hence, there is significant difference in the self confidence of Science and Arts Government Senior Secondary School Students. Hence the Hypothesis-IV “There will be significant difference in the mean scores of self-confidence of Government Senior Secondary School Students of Science and Arts streams” is accepted.

Table V

Showing Co-efficient of correlation (r) between Social Competence and Self-confidence of Government Senior Secondary School Students. of senior secondary school students.

Variable	No. of Sample (N)	Correlation (r)	Level of significance
Social competence	200	0.897**	Significant at 0.05 and
Self Confidence	200		0.01 level of significant

From table-V represents the co-efficient of co-relation between social competence and self confidence of Government Senior Secondary School Students. It comes out 0.897 which is significant at 0.05 and 0.01 levels of significance. Hence, there is significant relationship between social competence and self confidence of Government Senior Secondary School Students. Hence the Hypothesis-V “There will be a significant relationship between social competence and self-confidence of Government Senior Secondary School Students” is accepted.

Findings of the study

On the basis of result obtained after the interpretation of objectives and Hypotheses, the following findings have been drawn out:

1. There exists significant difference in the mean scores of social competence of Government Senior Secondary School Students with respect to gender.
2. There exists significant difference in the mean scores of social competence of Government Senior Secondary School Students of Science and Arts streams.
3. There exists significant difference in the mean scores of self-confidence of Government Senior Secondary School Students with respect to gender.
4. There exists significant difference in the mean scores of self-confidence of Government Senior Secondary School Students of Science and Arts streams.
5. There exists significant relationship between social competence and self-confidence of Government Senior Secondary School Students.

Conclusions

In the present study the investigator finds that there exists a significant relationship between Social Competence and Self Confidence of Government Senior Secondary School Students. The same was also found by [3] that Social competence includes not only behaviors but also cognitive skills which directs and facilitate children's social behaviors.

As same in study [13] the author concluded that parental attitude played a significant role in developing self-confidence ratings among children, It means if parents having good social competence than they can develop more self confidence among their children and also in study [10] author found that there exists significant relationship between self confidence and emotional maturity among the senior secondary school students.

It means that Self Confidence plays a significant role in attaining Social Competence of Government Senior Secondary School Students.

Educational Implications

- These results will give immense help to Researches, Guidance Workers, Teachers and School Counselors to develop suitable methods of teaching.

- These results will help the Teachers to develop healthy attitude among the students.
- These results could help the Teachers and mothers to know about the importance of self confidence in the life of their wards.
- These results will be very helpful for the Parents to develop healthy environment into their families.
- These results could help the teachers to develop congenial environment in the class.
- These results will give immense help to Teachers, Parents, Guidance Workers and School Counselors to enhance social competence and self confidence among Government Senior Secondary School Students.
- These results will give immense help in Curriculum Construction.
- These results will help the Teachers and parents to make students more social competent.
- These results will help the school Principals, Teachers and Parents to solve the problems of Government Senior Secondary School Students.
- These results have practical utility in the field of education as well as in the field of guidance and counseling.
- These results will help the parents to improve Parent-child relationship.
- These results will be very beneficial in the harmonious development of personality of Government Senior Secondary School Students.

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